

Gaussian Mixture Model for Battery Operation Anomaly Detection.

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Abstract — This research presents an anomaly detection algorithm for a Vanadium Redox Flow Battery (VRFB) using battery dataset as an example. The algorithm determines the anomaly detection threshold by fitting a Gaussian mixed model (GMM) to an anomaly-free dataset and testing it against a dataset containing only anomalies. By forcing the test dataset to classify all observations as anomalies, the threshold can be found. Applying again the model to the training dataset, classifies 11% of normal observations as failures, indicating that, not all observations were captured by the GMM, resulting in false positives. A percentage based on the likelihood values is suggested for replication to other systems, and a ratio of anomaly detection over time is proposed for preventive maintenance alerts.

Keywords — Mixed Gaussian model, Vanadium redox flow battery, Battery preventive maintenance, Anomaly detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy Storage Systems (ESS) are characterized by various variables that offer insights into the system's functioning and health [1]. However, analysing these high-dimensional models with conventional statistical or supervised machine learning methods, can be challenging [2] [3] due to the absence of validation data that can be directly linked to system failures. To overcome this challenge, this study used a dataset provided by an industrial partner of a real-life monitoring system of a Vanadium Redox Flow Battery (VRFB) with a total of 205500 observations with a 4-second time step and 11 measurement variables. The dataset is available upon request.

During the monitoring period, a non-catastrophic failure took place. A malfunctioning occurred in the electrolyte membrane inside the Vanadium battery deposit, which led to an erratic behaviour of the battery [4]. The log files were retrieved from the local battery management systems (BMS) and the time window under which the failure occurred was considered. The dataset was split into two sub datasets, one prior to the failure and another after the failure. The fact that the failure was non-catastrophic enabled the battery to keep operating under abnormal conditions, resulting in an abnormal performance, providing a valuable dataset for validation.

II. STATE OF THE ART

Anomaly detection is a critical task for ensuring reliable and efficient operation regardless of the sector. It has been applied to detecting cyber-attacks, fraud detection, quality control in manufacturing, structural integrity of buildings just to mention a few. It has also been applied in power systems, especially in power transformers, given their high cost, but also to distribution grids and power plants.

Authors in [5] addresses the challenge of integrating two-valued variables (0 or 1) with continuous variables for anomaly detection in applied to a thermal power plant. Traditional methods primarily rely on continuous variables and often discard two-valued data. The authors propose a

novel mixed hidden naive Bayesian model (MHNBM) that effectively utilizes both variable types to improve anomaly detection. The model's efficacy is demonstrated using data from Zhoushan power plant, China, showing enhanced detection performance.

Authors in [6] focus on classifying various anomalies in power system state estimation, such as bad data, sudden load changes, and false data injection attacks. Existing methods struggle to differentiate these anomalies, particularly between sudden load changes and false data injections. The authors propose a new algorithm combining analytical and machine learning (ML) approaches to detect anomalies, classify their types, and identify their origins. The algorithm's first stage uses an analytical approach to detect anomalies, while the second stage employs ML to classify the anomalies and identify their sources. Notably, the ML method is designed to be independent of network configuration, avoiding the need for retraining after topology changes. Testing on the IEEE 14 bus system shows the algorithm's accuracy and effectiveness.

Anomaly detection has also been applied to power transformers. In [7] a data-driven anomaly detection method is presented. For transformers with multiple working states and nonlinearity of data, adaptive kernel fuzzy C-means clustering (KFCM) algorithm is used to cluster sample data, each class corresponds to a working state. Then, the kernel principal component analysis (KPCA) is used to obtain projection matrices and anomaly detection limits of various classes. A method for online update of sample data is designed in this paper. Finally, the measured data of the power transformer is used for experiment, and the results are compared with the results obtained by using the conventional KPCA algorithm. The experimental results prove the correctness and effectiveness of the method in this paper.

Applied to a battery pack of electric vehicles, authors in [8] introduce a semi-supervised anomaly detection model for electric vehicle (EV) battery packs, aiming to prevent serious faults by identifying early anomalies before thermal runaway occurs. The proposed model utilizes a gated recurrent unit-based variational autoencoder (GRU-VAE) to detect these anomalies. The GRU captures complex time dependencies in multivariate time series data, while the VAE reconstructs the input data to identify potential abnormalities through reconstruction error. The Peaks over Threshold (POT) model from extreme value theory is used to set the detection threshold. Experiments with real EV datasets demonstrate the model's effectiveness in detecting potential anomalies, offering a valuable tool for enhancing battery safety.

Given the growing importance of energy storage systems, their continuous grid integration, their size and cost, the relevance for anomaly detection models to avoid operation disruption has increased.

The goal of this research is to leverage on the availability of a battery operation dataset with both normal and abnormal operation observations and to determine the correct threshold for anomaly detection to recommend preventive maintenance actions, avoiding catastrophic failures or system under performance [9].

To this end, this study considers the application of a Gaussian mixture model (GMM) [10] to this system. This approach is particularly used in multi-modal distributions, such as the one addressed here, in which data points cannot be well described by a single Gaussian curve, but instead by combining multiple Gaussian components. This may occur due to the existence of distinct functional regions, such as temperature, power or other.

Thus, a hypothesis (H) was created that states the following: - by fitting a GMM to a normal operation behaviour dataset, it is then possible to detect anomalies in the ESS functioning, by calculating the log-likelihood of a new entry of belonging to the Gaussian model, according to a pre-determined threshold, validated by an abnormal dataset. By proving this hypothesis, the authors present a simple and replicable approach to anomaly detection in ESS.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. The model rationale

The Gaussian Mixture Model used in this study is a probabilistic approach, assuming that the data is part of/generated from a mixture of several Gaussian distributions. It is a unsupervised model and it has been used for the detection of abnormal behaviours in different contexts and studies [11] [12] [13]. This approach starts by training a model, then performs density estimation, and finally defines a threshold. The first stage is an optimization exercise. The model is trained by optimizing the likelihood of the observed data with respect to the model parameters. The training process involves finding the values of the model parameters (mean, covariance matrix, and mixing coefficients) that maximize the likelihood of the observed data under the GMM.

The underlying algorithm is often referred to Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm [14], which alternates between two main steps: the Expectation step (E-step) and the Maximization step (M-step). In the E-step, the algorithm computes the posterior probability of each data point belonging to each of given set of Gaussian components. These posterior probabilities are calculated using the current estimates of the parameters (mean, covariance, and mixing coefficients) of the Gaussian components. In the M-step, the algorithm updates the parameters of the Gaussian components to maximize the log-likelihood of the data given the current set of parameters. The parameters include the mean, covariance, and mixing coefficients. This involves adjusting these parameters to better fit the data, ensuring that the Gaussian distributions capture the underlying structure of the data in an iterative process.

Each Gaussian distribution within the mixture represents a cluster or component in the data. The clusters, emerge because of the E-step, where each data point is probabilistically assigned to one of the Gaussian components based on its likelihood under each component's distribution. The parameters updated in the M-step, refine these clusters by adjusting the Gaussian distributions to better represent the

underlying data distribution. The combination of these Gaussians results in an overall Gaussian Mixture curve.

The second stage of this approach is density estimation. Once the GMM is trained, it can be used to estimate the probability density function (PDF) of the data. This involves calculating the probability of observing each data point under the learned mixture of Gaussians. Once this is done the likelihood of each data point being under the GMM can be evaluated.

The anomaly detection comes in the third step, based on the definition of a threshold. One can set a threshold to distinguish between normal and abnormal observations. Data points with likelihood scores below a defined threshold of likelihood are classified as anomalies. Points with low likelihood values are considered anomalies since they are less likely to have been generated by the learned distribution. This threshold can be determined based on the characteristics of the data and the desired trade-off between false positives and false negatives. The training data is specific to each system under study. However, a relative fit threshold applied to similar technologies or systems could be a valuable indicator, especially for those who did not have the chance to validate their models, due to the absence of faults, which is in the end what this study intends to provide.

B. The model implementation

The VRFB system was set up to receive command signals to either charge or discharge itself. During one of the discharging periods, a failure occurred, causing a rupture in the internal system's membrane. In Fig. 1 one can observe the exact moment when this non-catastrophic failure occurs, highlighted by the red ellipse, which later was attributed to a membrane rupture.

Fig. 1 Plot of the VRFB charge/discharge power over time. During one of the discharging periods the power rapidly drops from 2000W to 0 before rising again to 2000W.

As previously mentioned, the VRFB log file dataset was split into two sub datasets: pre-malfunction, and post-malfunction monitoring respectively, henceforward known as dataset A and dataset B respectively. This division becomes clear in Fig. 2 where one can observe the same plot as in Fig. 1 but expanding to a broader time period.

As one can observe by analysing Fig. 2, after the fault occurred, the battery was still operating but it was no longer able to operate according to commands or as expected, as the system started to respond erratically. It is important to highlight that the dataset made up of 11 variables, even though only two of them are demonstrated in the previous figures.

The other variables considered for the GMM application, along with Power and SOC, provide a statistical measure regarding the dynamics of the system in relation to the electric

behaviour. In other words, it provides a quantitative degree to which variables change together, which is the covariance.

Fig. 2 Original dataset and subsequent partition into datasets A and B. The data before dataset A were discarded from the analysis because it contained measurements from the system setup phase and does not represent normal operating data.

Based on the log files of the BMS and the work in [15] [16] the following variables were considered for the dataset:

1. Battery DC power in Watts [W].
2. Battery DC voltage in Volts [V].
3. Battery DC current in Amps [A].
4. Battery SOC in percentage [%].
5. Inverter phase 1 voltage in Volts [V].
6. Inverter phase 1 current in Amps [A].
7. Battery electrolyte temperature in degree Celsius [°C].
8. phase 1 average voltage in Volts [V].
9. phase 1 average current in Amps [A].
10. phase 1 average reactive power in kilo Volt-Amp reactive [kVAr].
11. phase 1 average power factor, 0 to 1.

TABLE I presents the statistical description of dataset A and its variables, and in TABLE II provides the statistical description of Dataset B and its variables.

IV. RESULTS DISCUSSION

From a quick analysis, an element stands out from the comparison between both datasets. There is an increase in standard deviation from 0.93 to 3.04 in the overall current measure (Inverter phase 1), while the other currents (DC and L1) do not report the same change. This is especially interesting if the mean value of the DC Power is also considered, where one can observe that the training dataset (dataset A) has a mean value of 740 W, whereas only a small decrease exists in the test dataset B, to 652 W.

The above-mentioned variables were measured at the points shown in Fig. 3. As one can observe, the measurements are collected at different points of the system, which provides the model with a broader overlook of the set-up as a whole and not just of a single point of the VRFB.

The GMM was then implemented in Python, by using scikit learn library [17], and fitted to dataset A (training stage). This allowed for the creation of a set of clusters, described by their Gaussian parameters such as mean, standard deviation and co-variance, which were considered to represent the normal functioning of the battery system.

TABLE I. STATISTICAL DESCRIPTION OF DATASET A. PRESENTING THE NUMBER OF DATAPPOINTS, THEIR MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION, MINIMUM AND MAXIMUM

Points of measurement as depicted in Fig. 3 and units						
	1 [W]	2 [V]	3 [A]	5 [V]	6 [A]	
count	74968.00					
mean	740.59	53.92	12.16	238.46	1.56	
std	1663.15	3.41	32.22	1.41	2.57	
min	-2805.0	44.00	-60.00	233.00	-4.00	
25%	1328.0	52.00	24.00	238.00	3.00	
50%	1608.0	54.00	29.00	238.00	3.00	
75%	1755.0	56.00	32.00	239.00	3.00	
max	2236.0	60.00	44.00	245.00	4.00	
Points of measurement as depicted in Fig. 3 and units						
	7 [°C]	8 [V]	9 [A]	10 [kVAr]	11 [0-1]	4 [%]
count	74968.00					
mean	28.27	239.31	3.93	0.65	-0.42	57.17
std	1.80	1.25	0.93	0.58	0.06	23.09
min	26.00	233.09	1.76	-2.45	-0.85	10.00
25%	27.00	238.50	4.07	0.91	-0.45	39.00
50%	28.00	239.34	4.36	0.96	-0.42	61.00
75%	29.00	240.13	4.48	0.98	-0.38	77.00
max	33.00	246.81	10.45	1.19	0.70	91.00

TABLE II. STATISTICAL DESCRIPTION OF DATASET B. PRESENTING THE NUMBER OF DATAPPOINTS, THEIR MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION, MINIMUM AND MAXIMUM

Points of measurement as depicted in Fig. 3 and units						
	1 [W]	2 [V]	3 [A]	5 [V]	6 [A]	
count	130543					
mean	652.946	56.589	10.873	237.995	1.773	
std	929.492	5.3266	16.330	1.451	1.412	
min	-6260	9	-150	230	-12	
25%	142	55	3	237	1	
50%	334	55	6	238	2	
75%	923	60	15	239	2	
max	7217	62	120	244	12	
Points of measurement as depicted in Fig. 3 and units						
	7 [°C]	8 [V]	9 [A]	10 [kVAr]	11 [0-1]	4 [%]
count	130543					
mean	26.164	239.095	5.722	-0.252	0.659	50.034
std	2.485	1.056	3.050	1.001	0.952	19.062
min	21	231.588	1.373	-5.012	-3.068	0
25%	24	238.748	2.734	-1.322	-0.408	40
50%	28	239.307	4.916	0.162	0.418	52
75%	28	239.307	8.906	0.480	1.670	68
max	33	244.844	21.077	3.028	2.239	71

Fig. 3 VRFB and Inverter setup. In this image the reader can observe where each measurement is carried out, and that the VRFB has a BMS and an AC cooling unit.

These were the results of maximizing the loglikelihood values to fit the overall resulting Gaussian mixture model. We use the loglikelihood values instead of only the likelihood ones because when dealing with small probabilities, the values can become very close to zero, leading to numerical underflow issues. Taking the logarithm of the likelihood transforms these small values into more manageable negative numbers, thus improving numerical stability in computations.

Fig. 4 shows the pertinence of using a mixture model, which is justified by having a multimodal dataset. This example shows the DC Battery current (top) and DC Battery power (bottom) with distinct operational zones. Other zones can be observed in the other variables and so, in order to capture the variety of the data, several distributions are considered with a resulting mixture. Other statistical mixtures exist such as the: Poisson Mixture Model, used for modelling count data, where each component in the mixture follows a Poisson distribution; the Exponential Mixture Model, which is suitable for modelling data with right-skewed distributions, such as survival times. In this case, each component in the mixture follows an exponential distribution or the Student's t Mixture Model, being similar to the Gaussian Mixture Model, but with heavier tails. More robust to outliers and can capture multimodal distributions better. These are just three examples among others. The use of the GMM in this context is due to the nature of the data, the flexibility and easiness to implement, its simplicity, interpretability, scalability and of course for being a well-established theory in various fields.

To decide on the number of components to use, and even to compare our approach with one that implemented a simple Gaussian fit, the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) [18], indicators were considered, which indicated that the best results would be achieved by considering 6 components. AIC strikes a balance between the goodness of fit of the model and its complexity while BIC is another model selection criterion that introduces a stronger penalty term for adding parameters. Like the AIC, the model with the lowest BIC value is preferred. However, the BIC penalizes complex models more heavily than the AIC, especially for large sample sizes. Both the AIC and BIC values are 10^5 orders of magnitude higher when considering only a simple Gaussian fit, instead of the GMM. Fig. 5 presents the Gaussian Mixture resulting curve with its individual components from 1 to 6 (clusters) for the DC Voltage example. The bars that appear almost overlapped near the x-values of 53 and 59 in the "DC Voltage Battery V" subplot indicate that for those voltage values, multiple components have very similar voltage readings.

Fig. 4 Dataset A distributions for Battery DC current in Amps (Top) and Battery DC Power in Watts (Bottom). Y-axis represents frequency of occurrences.

This just means that the voltage distributions of several components closely align or coincide and that those components are exhibiting similar behaviour or operating conditions at those voltage levels.

Fig. 5 Histogram for Dataset A for the DC Voltage variable (x-axis Value), showing the 6 components and the resulting Gaussian Mixture curve.

These criteria balance the goodness of fit with the complexity of the model, penalizing models that are too complex. Both AIC and BIC consider the likelihood of the data and the number of parameters in the model. The lower the AIC or BIC value, the better the model is considered. If the AIC or BIC values are substantially lower, as it is the case, for the GMM compared to the single Gaussian model, it suggests that the GMM captures more complex patterns in the data and is a better fit [19]. Fig. 6 shows the components or clusters considered, with the example of two variables, system voltage and DC Power of the battery. Two regions stand out for the nominal power that the battery was operating at the time. These are charging at 2000 W and discharging at 2000 W. A third region in the middle corresponding to cluster 3 correspond to the moments in which the battery was close to zero or not working operating at all.

Fig. 6 Scatter plot with 6 clusters, the x-axis represents the Battery DC Power while the y-axis represents the average voltage of phase 1 at the energy analyser measurement point. The left super cluster is mainly composed of cluster's 1 and 4 while the right super cluster is composed of cluster's 0, 2 and 5.

By testing the dataset B under the trained model and having defined a threshold, we could obtain a classification of “True” or “False” (anomaly or not) for each observation. However, we already know that the Dataset B contained 100% of anomalies. In this case, we iterate the module to provide the log-likelihood value to the point in which 100% of all observations are considered “True” anomalies, thus providing the fine-tuned threshold. Dataset A was also tested against the trained model with the new threshold to verify if no anomalies were detected within it. The model flow is presented in Fig. 7.

Dataset B was 100% classified as “True” anomalies as expected. Dataset A was also tested and resulted in 11% “True” classification, meaning that 11% of those datapoints were not captured by the GMM, hence seen as false positives. A percentage based on all the amplitude of log-likelihood values of all observations against the threshold is presented as an indication for replication to other systems.

In this case instead of using the maximum and minimum, the maximum and median were used to remove outliers.

This resulted in a threshold percentage placement at 2.37% away from the maximum log-likelihood value. To transform this model into a replicable service, a ratio of abnormal events within a time-period was created, notifying the operator when more than one anomaly per each 12 h (adjustable) is detected, triggering an alert message for preventive maintenance. For each battery type, the model must be trained with specific data.

This research approach improves ESS predictive maintenance by detecting malfunctions in monitored data and determining the threshold for anomaly classification using trained data. Future applications include using benchmark data from ESS manufacturers to detect anomalies, during operation and prevent system failures, aiding ESS operators with similar technologies and thresholds as benchmarks.

With the advent of connected data spaces, maintenance related services can be developed that leverage on these technologies to share data for a common benefit of learning with other systems.

V. CONCLUSION

This research has presented a successful implementation of a model able to classify anomalies in an energy storage system operation. It is important to clear that the model by itself does not categorize anomalies or malfunctions into specific types but only in a binary format, for the purpose of this work a malfunction is defined as an occurrence outside normal operating conditions, that when repeated over time can cause the need for preventive maintenance.

Further work must be carried out as further testing is required with different datasets and technologies, especially to understand if the relative threshold could be a fit value for other systems. This study only considered one energy storage system, that used a single battery technology, Vanadium, and only one type of malfunction caused. As more and more datasets are available it would be possible to understand how

Fig. 7 Workflow of proposed fault detection system. As the reader can observe, the fault detection mechanism is in a constate state of update because the sensitivity value can evolve as the system is under operation, as well as the threshold value.

the threshold could change and to distinguish between normal and abnormal measurement types.

A key advantage of applying this model comes from the fact that the model only needs to be fitted once, to the anomaly free dataset. once this is done the subsequent measures can be compared via the threshold, this is not necessarily true with other methods of machine learning in each frequent training is desired, especially if supervised approaches are taken. It is also worth mentioning that the threshold definition comes with a trade-off between having false positives or false negatives. For critical assets, it is desired to incur higher false positives than false negatives and mitigate this with triggering indicators, such as the proposed ratio of abnormal observations over time, which could be made more flexible or strict according to experience.

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